

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: PANTUVO****FIRST NAME: JERRY****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Basic steps in essay writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Avoiding plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-9)
3. Citation format (EUCLID 2019, 11-12)
4. Proper use of approved rules of style (EUCLID 2019, 24-26)
5. Avoiding common grammatical errors (EUCLID 2019, 17-23)
6. Basic differences between American and British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
7. Chicago style and usage (EUCLID 2019, 44-55)

INTRODUCTION TO ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I consider the ACA-401 course a good place to start my PhD. Going through the Coursepack, I realized there were a lot of assumptions in my knowledge on academic writing. Going through the carefully selected topics that make up the Coursepack, it dawned on me that the reason I have not written so many journal articles is because I had always taken essay writing as a linear process. In this course, I have learnt the basic steps in essay writing; how to avoid plagiarism; the EUCLID citation format; proper use of approved rules of styles; the basic differences between American and British English; and the Chicago style and usage.

The Coursepack, presented the topics in a sequential order, that made going through them engaging. It also included a video that presented how to install and use Zotero, and an instructor that was prompt to respond to my enquiries. My knowledge of Refworks and Mendeley citation managers was helpful in quickly finding my way with Zotero. Adding Zotero to the collection of citation managers I can use was an exciting discovery. I look forward to building on what I have learnt so far. Hopefully, I will become a proficient essay writer, with many peer-reviewed papers published, by the time I am through with my doctorate studies.

2) STARTING RIGHT

Academic essays are unique in their presentation because they aim to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence. Therefore, a good academic essay should have a good thesis statement that answers the main question with an argument as well as discuss these arguments using closely related points with evidence and relevant examples from credible sources to support the argument (EUCLID 2019, 1).

Writing a successful essay starts with a good plan. The plan should be flexible and outline your initial thoughts and ideas. As one researches the topic or answers to the main questions, one is bound to find new information that should be noted down and used as needed. It is important to have enough time to research, review and have opinions of others before finalizing the essay (ibid.). Every essay should have an introduction, a body and a conclusion. The introduction should be brief and provide a summary of the essay. The body answers the main questions in paragraphs that discuss the main points with evidence to support each argument, whilst the conclusion restates the question and summarizes the discussions (EUCLID 2019, 3)

One challenge I always had as a writer is that of achieving a logical flow to my points. I realized after going through this Coursepack that it may be because I do not give myself enough time from starting to finishing the essay, and because I am unsure what to reference and what not to reference. Citing to avoid plagiarism resonated well with me because I am proficient in using citation managers like Mendeley, Refworks and Endnote. In fact, using citation managers make citing other people's work a lot easier to do that the temptation to overcite is always there. However, the temptation to cite almost everything, use convoluted sentences to show off one's knowledge, and have a long list of cited works are bad practices that I have learnt to avoid. One basic rule on when not to cite that I learnt is that "if it is repeated in many different sources that you have read, then you can assume it is common knowledge" (EUCLID 2019, 5-10).

3) DOING YOUR HOMEWORK

A good essay does not just happen because one is knowledgeable about the subject matter. It requires diligence, commitment and attention to details. I have learnt that I must have the time and discipline to research other viewpoints or counter arguments to the ones I hold. I cannot make sweeping generalities without evidence to support those arguments. In fact, I have learnt to argue against myself when I make criticism. It is safer to assume that the counter argument is from a rational person whose viewpoint might have been subjected to rigorous debates in the past (EUCLID 2019, 14).

Therefore, writing an effective essay requires the discipline to research, gather evidence and organize one's ideas in a logical manner. It also requires paying attention to details like when an apostrophe should come before or after the "s," how many spaces go after a period, what are the proper uses of "your" and "you're," and whether or not a comma is needed before the "and" in a list of items (EUCLID 2019, 18-19).

To be frank, this is the first time I am coming across the Turabian style. I had used the Harvard Coventry style in the past and never really got to research other styles. It was a fascinating discovery to find such rich collection of guides on the Turabian style. I have read the argument for or against the use of styles guides, I tend to agree with the reason for having a guide that enforces consistency. One other advantage of a style guide I learnt is that it saves time in proofreading and correcting manuscripts (EUCLID 2019, 24–25). However, I noticed that the Chicago manual style and the Turabian are used in the Coursepack as though they are the same. This leaves me wondering why they both appear in the Zotero style manager list.

As a Nigerian, my British colonial root has made me deliberately change my computer to British English Style whenever I get a new computer. Now, I realize I must adjust to the American style for my doctorate studies. It is interesting to note also that the American English is currently the dominant influence on “World English” with very convincing reasons enumerated (EUCLID 2019, 27). The extent to which American and British English differ is by far larger than I thought. I now know, I will have to keep looking up references when I write, in order to stay consistent with the American English in all my writings, going forward.

4) OBSERVATIONS

The Coursepack has helped me to feel confident starting my term paper. The template helped me to save time formatting my work, and it was easy to use. After going through the Coursepack and ready to begin writing my term paper, I tried my hands on Zotero but noticed my bibliography was different from the way it was written in the Coursepack. I went through the video provided, repeatedly, hoping to discover how to import the citation into Zotero. I had to resort to manually input the citation into Zotero. When I added the bibliography, I had to manually edit it to fit into the Turabian style.

My writing inertia should be over after taking this course. I feel confident to start and finish a paper in record time after having grasped the skill to organize my thoughts, properly structure my essay, research my topics and cite appropriately. The importance of starting my essays the right way cannot be overemphasized. Going forward, I will always start early, give myself time to research my ideas and organize my points in a logical way. My knowledge in using citation managers has been enhanced. I am now more aware of what and what not to cite. I have also become more conscious of common grammatical errors I make when writing. Hopefully, these errors will reduce dramatically by the time and I am through with my doctorate studies. Despite efforts in highlighting the differences between American and British English in the Coursepack, the resources shared will continue to serve as a reference material in ensuring consistency in my writing.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

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